

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NZAU****FIRST NAME: FRANCISCA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The essence of good essay Writing (EUCLID 2021,7-12)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
3. American VS British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-31)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021,33-39)
5. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I felt a strong urge to challenge my current knowledge level and started to check online for colleges that offer exclusive online classes for a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program. I identified [Euclid University](#) and registered for the online courses immediately. The orientation pack was emailed to me by the [university](#), and I started reading it to familiarize myself with the course program. I have read the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack material, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. [Kabiru Gulma](#), that contains the steps to good professional paper writing. In addition, I have watched tutorial videos on Grammarly plagiarism checker and Zotero.

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To finish my studies on time, I have learned not to wait to take notes after reading but instead to take notes as I read. The notes are helpful when writing the response papers. Response papers aim to assess the student's understanding of what the [lecturer](#) is teaching. Therefore, in this response paper, I am glad to discuss the essence of good essay writing with proper punctuation, correct English in the essay: American VS British English, Plagiarism, and a practical style guide.

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2) THE ESSENCE OF A GOOD WRITING

An academic essay is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work, and its purpose is to provide answers to hypotheses to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2021, 1). A good essay gives insights into one's thoughts and a clear understanding of the research under discussion.

To produce a good essay, one has to prepare very well in terms of time and devotion to the topic. Planning is critical for a well-structured essay paper. A plan helps writers put their ideas systematically (EUCLID 2021, 7). I agree with the tips for effective and best essay writing because if correctly adhered to, the outcome is a quality essay (EUCLID 2021, 11). A writer may have limited time to complete the paper if they delve into reading the whole topic without making a plan.

As a learning process for good essay writing, rules of thumb must be adhered to to produce an authentic essay. One has to state the main thesis of their paper and stay on course during the writing period and stay away from general and or sweeping statements that add no value to the paper. I have also learned that one has to write an interesting essay that will motivate the readers to read it and create a lasting impression. If one uses a source that is not his or hers, it is crucial to indicate the source of information. In other words, one should not take credit for using other writers' information (EUCLID 2021, 13-14). Claiming ownership of the words or ideas of other writers is an act of plagiarism, and it is discouraged by all means and can make one face consequences if they do not recognize the source.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

I have noted that an essay requires good punctuation to communicate and emphasize various issues. There are different types of punctuation marks like apostrophes, Brackets, Bullet points, colon and semicolons, and commas, to name but a few (EUCLID 2021, 16-19). The punctuation must be applied correctly to bring out the sentence's intended meaning.

The author put it clearly when to use punctuation and the type of punctuation to be used. I must confess that I have been misapplying some punctuation marks, and this coursepack has empowered me to use them correctly.

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4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The British Colony colonized Kenya, and this influenced how the English language was to be spoken and written. Therefore, in Kenya, the Standard language spoken and written is Standard British English.

With the growth and emergence of Technology, Standard American English seems to be adopted by many teaching organizations, and Euclid University is not an exception.

Factors like the United States Politics, Economics, Technology, and cultural influences have played a significant part in adopting Standard American English. An example is the date format which starts with the month, date, and year. For a long time, the date format was the day, month, and year. Also, American and British English have some words with the exact spelling and with different pronunciations and vice versa (Euclid 2021,25). Furthermore, both languages use different quotations to emphasize similar points. For example, In Standard British English, inverted commas are used; 'The boy kicked the ball' versus "The boy kicked the ball." US quotation marks, (EUCLID 2021,31).

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5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). The Encyclopedia Britannica has defined plagiarism as "the act of taking another person's writing and passing them off as one's own." A literature review contains information researched by other writers, and it is essential to recognize their work. I have learned that plagiarism is punishable if an author does not acknowledge the source of information. For example, students may fail their exams if they use other students' knowledge and do not recognize it in their essays. Therefore, I have resolved to avoid plagiarism in my work so that I do not suffer its consequences.

There are two significant ways a writer can give credit to a source of their information: quotations and paraphrases (EUCLID 2021,35-36). The in-text citation is used to acknowledge other people's work, and quotation marks too. Paraphrasing is the act of using own words to describe what the author says. In addition, paraphrasing is when one rewrites any part/paragraph of a manuscript in their own words. It is a statement of someone else's ideas in one's own.

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Furthermore, if one uses data or graphs borrowed from other sources, one should recognize them through citing. Again, one has to guard against over-citing and paraphrasing to maintain the originality of one's work. There are times when citing does not add value, like when the information is common knowledge and readily available. The best way for a student or a writer is to practice ethical writing honestly by crediting all the sources.

According to EUCLID 2021, the authors have highly discouraged any form of plagiarism. They guide that the best way to avoid it is by always citing the source of information used.

6) STYLE GUIDES

According to EUCLID (2021, 24), a style guide is a means of documenting one's approach to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. In addition, a style guide establishes the basic rules or features of one's writing for consistency in the written output.

Chicago Manual Style and American English are the most preferred and recommended in EUCLID to maintain standards in the documents produced. There are as many style guides as there are several writers: examples of the most common ones: The American Psychological Association (APA) and the Modern Language Association (MLA). One chooses the style guide as recommended by the organization.

I learned how to insert the referencing using Zotero through a video tutorial demonstration by Cleenwerck Laurent, 2021. Once the Zotero App is downloaded and installed, the referencing is easy to insert as one writes the essay.

7) CONCLUSION

A student must adhere to the rules and regulations of writing an essay to produce a good paper. The course pack has helped me to understand the essence of good essay writing. I have gained insights on the type of English to use while writing essays and the style guide towards good academic writing. I have also read what plagiarism is and when how to avoid it in my academic papers so that I do not suffer the consequences of plagiarism.

Additionally, one needs to plan well and stick to the topic. This can be achieved by creating a structured process for writing the essay.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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